

An overview of global path planning methods for mobile robots for industrial applications

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Abstract—This article presents an overview of one of the main problems in mobile robotics: path planning. It consists in finding a geometric collision-free path from a certain initial configuration to a final one. In particular, the global formulation requires the workspace to be fully known in order to generate a complete path avoiding obstacles before the robot begins its movement and, for this reason, the most well-known techniques of geometric representation of the environment are presented.

Index Terms—Mobile robotics, Path planning, Environment Representation

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile robotics is applied successfully in many areas, both industrial and civil, in order to increase productivity, enhance safety and provide services. One of the most crucial research problems on this topic is path planning, which consists in finding a collision-free path for the robot to reach the desired destination in order to accomplish its task. In general, path planning [1] requires a description of the geometry of the robot, which can be defined as a single rigid body or as a union of links. The robot operates in a workspace that can be planar or three-dimensional, and that can be divided in two regions: one free and one occupied by obstacles. These regions are mapped in the robot's configuration space, resulting in an obstacle configuration space C_{obs} and a free space C_{free} . Finally, geometric continuous path belonging to C_{free} that connects an initial configuration q_{init} and a goal one q_{goal} can be computed.

This paper provides an overview of the methodologies used in mobile robotics for path planning and is organised as follows: Section II introduces the main techniques for modelling the environment from a geometric point of view such as cell decomposition, while Section III presents some of the global path planning methods belonging to the graph-based and sampling-based categories.

II. ENVIRONMENT REPRESENTATION

There are three main ways of representing the environment [2]: geometric, topological and semantic. These can be defined a priori or determined through mobile robot mapping operations using on-board sensors. Since path planning is a problem that concerns the determination of a geometric path

connecting an initial pose with a goal this paper focuses on modelling the workspace from a geometric point of view. In particular, there are two types of geometric environment modelling:

- **Feature-Based map representation:** a feature map accurately represents the positions of the features in a continuous space. It is usually built by mobile robots that detect their distance from surrounding objects using on-board range-and-bearing sensors, such as sonar or lidar. Data from these sensors can be used to identify lines using filtering algorithms. Subsequently, the lines can be joined to form the boundaries of objects in the workspace.
- **Free-Space representation:** this type of map represents the free space in which the robot can move, which is derived from knowledge of the position and shape of obstacles. The entire configuration space can be used, but usually in mobile robotics it is more convenient to use Cartesian coordinates in combination with collision detection algorithms to check whether a state is feasible or not. Furthermore, in order to cope with the fact that robots have a physical embodiment, free-state representation is defined in such a way that the robot is reduced to a point and all obstacles are expanded at least by half of the robot's longest extension. Obstacles can be modelled as polygons, obtaining free space accordingly, but the most popular technique belonging to this category is cell decomposition, which will be described below.

A. Cell decomposition

Cell decomposition consists in dividing the environment into cells that can be of two types: occupied or free. In this way, a grid is constructed that represents the portions of space that can be traversed by the mobile robot. The implementation of this strategy consists in:

- dividing the workspace into a grid formed by cells,
- determining whether the cell is occupied or unoccupied by defining an occupancy threshold.

In cases where high resolution without heavy memory consumption is desired, the Quadtree method is used [3]. With this technique, an irregular grid with non-uniform resolution is constructed iteratively by dividing each occupied cell into quadrants until the desired precision is achieved.

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Usually the grid is composed of squares, but there are cell decomposition techniques, such as those described in [4] and [5], that use tessellation with several regular polygons such as triangles or hexagons.

III. PATH PLANNING

This section presents the most popular global path planning techniques for mobile robots, belonging to the graph-based and sampling-based categories.

A. Graph Based

Graph-based path planning algorithms are very popular in mobile robotics because of their simplicity and efficiency. They make it possible to derive the path from the environment, the initial pose and the goal pose of the robot by solving an optimization problem that may involve several minimization criteria, such as [6]:

- Travel time
- Jerking
- Energy
- Path Length
- Hybrid criteria

The most famous graph search algorithms [7] are:

- Dijkstra's Algorithm
- A* Algorithm
- D* Algorithm

The following describes the types of graphs that can be used for path planning of a mobile robot.

1) *Roadmap*: A roadmap is a graph built upon nodes connected by edges. Each node represents a point in C_{free} , whereas each edge indicates how the robot evolves from one state to another. In static environments, where planning robustness is a priority, usually a static roadmap is used which can be defined manually or using automatic strategies, such as Voronoi diagrams [8] or Visibility graphs [9]. The former allows for the construction of such a roadmap that maximizes clearance between polygonal obstacles while the latter generates the Euclidean shortest path among them.

2) *Grid map graph*: In this strategy, the grid map is used as a graph in which each cell is represented by a node and is connected to adjacent ones by edges. The connectivity between cells can follow the Von Neumann or Moore's topology [10]. In both cases, the angles formed by the path belong to a finite set of values. To solve this limitation, graph search algorithms of the any angle type such as Theta* [11] can be used. This algorithm is very similar to A* but allows connecting nodes belonging to nonadjacent cells as long as there is line of sight between them. In the case of path planning of car-like robots, Hybrid A* [12] is often used, which exploits the A* strategy in combination with a state transition function in order to generate a path that respects limits on minimum curvature and nonholonomic constraints.

3) *State Lattice*: The state lattice [13] is used for robots with important nonholonomic constraints (such as car-like), and is based on discretizing the space state through a finite set of primitives by constraining the robot's mobility to a lattice graph that forms a regular and repeated pattern. Each type of primitive can be associated with a cost, and for this reason a graph search algorithm can be used to find the path.

B. Sampling Based

These algorithms base their working principle on sampling points in the robot configuration space and connecting them to obtain a path belonging to C_{free} that connects the initial and destination pose. They are widely used to solve the problem of path planning in a high-dimensional configuration space, such as in the case of manipulators, but are also successfully used in mobile robotics.

In general, sampling-based planners are probabilistically complete, that is, the probability that they will produce a solution and that it will be optimal approaches 1 as more time or iterations of the algorithm are spent. However, they cannot determine if no solution exists. The most popular sampling-based path planning strategies are Probabilistic RoadMap (PRM) and Rapidly exploring Random Trees (RRT).

1) *PRM*: Probabilistic RoadMap [14] is a multi-query technique whose goal is to map the connectivity of C_{free} . Its working principle is based on sampling configurations and construct a graph to be used to connect any pair of q_{init} and q_{goal} . Each sampled point is connected to an existing one using a local planning technique. For example, a simple interpolation of the two configurations can be used, resulting in a straight line. Then it is tested whether the link belongs to C_{free} . If this condition is verified the node and the edge are added to the graph. Once the graph reflecting the connectivity of C_{free} is completed, q_{init} and q_{goal} are connected to it with the local planner. Finally, a path is obtained exploiting the graph search techniques seen in the previous subsection.

2) *RRT*: Rapidly exploring Random Tree [15] is a single-query path planner that focuses on building and extending a tree data structure that connects a given pair (q_{init} , q_{goal}). In this way, path exploration occurs incrementally and for this reason it is suitable for dynamic environments, since the path is computed every single time. The working principle of RRT is iterative and is based on the following operations:

- sampling of a point in configuration space,
- determination of the point (q_{near}) of the tree closest to it,
- determination of the new state q_{new} , based on the maximum incremental step set,
- checking that the path connecting q_{new} and q_{near} belongs to C_{free} and, if so, addition of it to the tree.

Expansion continues until a solution is found, or alternatively, in some versions such as RRT* [16], it continues in a way that increases path optimality. Moreover, RRT algorithms can be classified according to the number of trees that are constructed simultaneously:

- Unidirectional, which involve a single tree, usually rooted at q_{init} ,
- Bidirectional, which involve two trees, typically rooted at q_{init} and q_{goal} ,
- Multidirectional, which may have more than two trees.

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